

The team gets bigger!

MetaDocencia

In September, three people joined the team (yes, 3!) after an open call for a project coordinator. We also started working with other communities to broaden participation in Open Science, and we are registering the contribution of external collaborators who support us in fulfilling our [mission and vision](#).

In September, we onboarded three new persons to the team (yes, 3!) following an open call for a project coordination role that had more than 130 applicants from 11 countries in Latin America. This decision aims to enhance the values of inclusion, diversity, community, and versatility of our team, articulating valuable and diverse backgrounds to better prepare us for the [next stage](#).

The selection process was hard and competitive. Considering the diversity of applications, we prioritized as essential requirements for these roles:

- Previous experience collaborating with MetaDocencia or graduating from an OLS Open Science training cohort;
- Experience in Open Science;
- Experience with responsible data analysis and reporting; and
- At least a very good spoken English.

We proudly introduce you to our new team members:

- [José Luis Vilca Villegas](#), a physician and scientist currently pursuing a Master's degree in Clinical Research. As part of a professional network encompassing research and editing in scientific publications, José Luis leads Conectorial, is part of the OLS community, and has previously participated in MetaDocencia and several other Open Science projects.
José Luis joins our team as a trainee and will take part in measuring our impact.
- [María Nanton](#) is a social communicator, currently pursuing a Master's degree in Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery. She actively participates in MetaDocencia, R-Ladies Buenos Aires, The Turing Way, and other communities

of practice around Open Science in Latin America. In the last few years, she has worked as a teacher in multiple undergraduate and graduate courses and as a data analyst in the public and private sectors, particularly with sensitive data. She will work on coordinating projects related to collaborative infrastructures and impact measurement.

- [Sabrina López](#) is a Ph.D. in Biological Sciences specializing in health data science and a Professor of Biology in High School and Higher Education. She has experience in interdisciplinary research in neuroscience, the responsible use of health data, and university teaching. She actively participates in MetaDocencia, OLS, and other Open Science communities. She will work on collaborative research projects with international communities.

We welcome José Luis, María, and Sabrina to the team!

Also, to honor the many incredible people who approached us in this and previous calls, we will share open activities over the coming weeks to continue creating bonds and expanding the [Hive of Fellow Communities](#).

We are so happy to grow as a community!

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Here is the citation we recommend you use: MetaDocencia Team (2023). The team gets bigger!. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10018150>